

Temperature dependent optical property studies of nematic mixtures

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Received 7 December 2005; accepted 24 April 2006

The refractive indices n_e and n_o , of two nematic mixtures: ZLI 2141-000 and ZLI 2452 have been measured in the temperature range 291-391 K using 589 nm light source. A slight modification to the four-parameter model given in Li *J et al.*, *J Appl Phys*, 96 (2004) 19, is made to carry out the analysis of the data. The temperature dependence of refractive indices and the birefringence agree closely with that obtained using four-parameter model. Different parameters have been compared. The value of parameter β is larger for ZLI 2452 than for ZLI 2141-000, which may be due to the presence of BCH in place of CB component in the latter. A linear relation is observed between birefringence (Δn) and the order parameter (S). The normalized polarizabilities: $\alpha_e / \langle \alpha \rangle$, $\alpha_o / \langle \alpha \rangle$ and the order parameter S agree fairly well with those obtained using modified model.

Keywords: Birefringence, Order parameter, Polarizability, Liquid crystals, Nematic mixtures

IPC Code: G02F1/13

1 Introduction

Liquid crystals (LC) possess many interesting and useful properties and find applications in many devices, such as LC displays¹, surface plasmon resonance sensors², tunable microlenses³, digital holography⁴, temperature sensors⁵, optical data storage⁶, and light modulators⁷. Some of the parameters useful for applications are birefringence⁸, dielectric measurements⁹, elastic constants¹⁰, diamagnetic anisotropy¹⁰, pretilt angle¹¹, polar anchoring coefficients¹², thermodynamical properties¹³, photographic textures¹⁴, density¹⁵ and conductivity¹⁶. Birefringence is mainly determined as a function of its constituents¹⁷, wavelength of incident light¹⁸ and its temperature⁸. The temperature plays an important role in affecting the LC refractive indices.

In the present paper, the extraordinary refractive index (n_e), ordinary refractive index (n_o) in liquid crystal phase and isotropic refractive index (n_i) in isotropic phase of two LC samples ZLI 2141-000 and ZLI 2452 as a function of temperature using Abbe refractometer with a monochromatic light source have been measured. The samples were procured from E Merck, Germany and used without further purification. The preliminary data of these two samples are given in Table 1.

A slight modification has been made to the four-parameter model of Li *J et al.*¹⁹, describing the temperature dependence of LC refractive indices. From the experimental data, different useful parameters; birefringence (Δn), normalized polarizabilities ($\alpha_e / \langle \alpha \rangle$, $\alpha_o / \langle \alpha \rangle$) and order parameter (S) have been calculated. The experimental data have been linked to the theoretically calculated values. It is observed that this model satisfies the experimental data very well. In addition, the modified Vuks equation²⁰ and semi-empirical relationship²¹ have been verified.

2 Experimental Details

The Abbe refractometer (accuracy 0.001) has been used for measuring both refractive indices (n_e and n_o). The refractometer was pre-calibrated by measuring the refractive indices of distilled water and benzene. A stable homogeneous alignment, unaffected by temperature cycling⁸, was induced in the present case by coating prism's surfaces with a thin film of polyvinyl alcohol (concentration 0.75% in water) and rubbing unidirectionally repeatedly. Such a method favoured uniform alignment with nematic director parallel to rubbing direction. The PVA coating does not affect the values of refractive indices⁸. Few drops

Table 1 — Preliminary data of two samples

Samples	Components	S -> N (°C)	Melting (°C)	Clearing (°C)	n_e	n_o
ZLI 2141-000	PCH/CB/ESTER Mixture	<-10	-3	+69	1.639	1.493
ZLI 2452	PCH/BCH/ESTER Broad Mixture	<-40	-20	+110	1.636	1.506

of LC sample were allowed to fall on both the prism surfaces and were spread with a spatula and lower prism was clamped to the position. A sodium light source (589 nm) is used for illuminating the sample. A converging lens is placed between the lamp and refractometer. The temperature of the sample in Abbe refractometer is controlled using circulating water/glycerine from a constant temperature bath. The temperature regulation was better than ± 0.1 K. For temperature up to 368 K, water is used for circulation, while hot glycerine is used for temperature starting from 363 K and above. To prevent heat loss, proper insulation is made at various points. To measure the temperature of the LC sample, a pre-calibrated copper-constantan thermocouple is placed in the closed vicinity of sample and connected with a sensitive digital micro voltmeter. The temperature of thermostat was increased in steps of 3 K for each measurement and kept constant for half-an-hour. A polaroid sheet is placed over the eyepiece to allow the distinct separation of dark and bright regions in the eyepiece²² corresponding to n_e and n_o (from Table 1 $n_e > n_o$). The transition temperature of both the samples was measured by texture study using polarizing microscope fitted with a hot stage arrangement and high-resolution CCD camera connected to PC. The observations on a particular sample conducted on three successive days showed no significant deviation and an average has been reported here.

3 Theory

Due to anisotropic nature of liquid crystals, these possess two refractive indices, n_e and n_o . Vuks²³ proposed a semi-empirical equation that correlates the microscopic molecular polarizabilities to macroscopic refractive indices for anisotropic medium considering local field to be isotropic.

$$(n_{e,o}^2 - 1) / (\langle n^2 \rangle + 2) = (4\pi/3) N \alpha_{e,o} \quad \dots(1)$$

where n_e and n_o are refractive indices for the extraordinary and ordinary rays, respectively. α_e and

α_o are respective molecular polarizabilities. N is the number of molecules per unit volume and $\langle n^2 \rangle$ is defined by the equation:

$$\langle n^2 \rangle = (n_e^2 + 2n_o^2) / 3 \quad \dots(2)$$

Since the sample alignment is planar, the optical anisotropy (Δn) is given by the difference between n_e and n_o , i.e.,

$$\Delta n = n_e - n_o \quad \dots(3)$$

$$n_e = n_o + \Delta n \quad \dots(4)$$

Using Eqs (2) and (4), we get a quadratic equation in n_o , given as:

$$3n_o^2 + 2(\Delta n) n_o + (\Delta n)^2 - 3\langle n^2 \rangle = 0 \quad \dots(5)$$

which gives

$$n_o = (1/3) [(9\langle n^2 \rangle - 2(\Delta n)^2]^{1/2} - (1/3)(\Delta n)$$

$$n_o = (\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2} [1 - (2/9)((\Delta n)^2 / \langle n^2 \rangle)]^{1/2} - (1/3)(\Delta n)$$

$$n_o = (\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2} [1 - (1/9)((\Delta n)^2 / \langle n^2 \rangle) + \dots + \dots] - (1/3)(\Delta n) \quad \dots(6)$$

The calculation from experimental data shows that the value of $[(1/9)(\Delta n)^2 / \langle n^2 \rangle]$ is about 0.08% of 1. Thus leaving this and other higher order terms, we get:

$$n_o = (\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2} - (1/3)(\Delta n) \quad \dots(7)$$

Using Eqs (3) and (7)

$$n_e = (\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2} + (2/3)(\Delta n) \quad \dots(8)$$

Li J *et al.*¹⁹ have described n_e and n_o as a function of $\langle n \rangle$ and Δn in the form:

$$n_o = \langle n \rangle - (1/3)(\Delta n) \quad \dots(9)$$

Table 2 — Values of slope, intercept and norms of residues

Sample	Parameter	Slope ($\times 10^{-4}$)	Intercept	Norms of Residues ($\times 10^{-3}$)
ZLI 2141-000	$\langle n \rangle$	-5.301	1.700	4.675
	$\langle n^2 \rangle$	-16.982	2.890	15.060
	$(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$	-5.533	1.709	4.955
ZLI 2452	$\langle n \rangle$	-4.847	1.691	9.720
	$\langle n^2 \rangle$	-15.211	2.850	29.890
	$(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$	-4.989	1.697	10.026

$$n_e = \langle n \rangle + (2/3)\Delta n \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\text{where } \langle n \rangle = (n_e + 2n_o)/3 \quad \dots(11)$$

Using experimental data for n_e and n_o , we have calculated the values of $\langle n \rangle$, $\langle n^2 \rangle$ and $(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$ and a linear fit is given in all three cases and values of slope, intercept and norms of residues are shown in Table 2.

From Table 2, the norms of residues for $\langle n \rangle$ and $(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$ are of the same order while for $\langle n^2 \rangle$ it is about 3 times to that of $(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$. Using a different approach $(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$ can be taken as a 1st order function of temperature T .

$$(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2} = A + BT \quad \dots(12)$$

On the other hand, LC birefringence (Δn) is given by Haller²⁴ and Wu²⁵

$$\Delta n(T) = (\Delta n)_0 (1 - T/T_c)^\beta \quad \dots(13)$$

where $(\Delta n)_0$ is the birefringence at $T = 0$ K, T_c is clearing temperature and β is a constant. Taking logarithm of Eq. (13) and giving linear fit, the values of $(\Delta n)_0$ and β are obtained.

Using Eqs (7), (8), (12) and (13), the equations for n_e and n_o are:

$$n_e = A + BT + (2/3)(\Delta n)_0 (1 - T/T_c)^\beta \quad \dots(14)$$

$$n_o = A + BT - (1/3)(\Delta n)_0 (1 - T/T_c)^\beta \quad \dots(15)$$

The rate of change of n_e and n_o with respect to temperature²⁶ (dn_e/dT , dn_o/dT) are:

$$dn_e/dT = B - (2/3)(\beta(\Delta n)_0/T_c) (1 - T/T_c)^{\beta-1} \quad \dots(16)$$

$$dn_o/dT = B + (1/3)(\beta(\Delta n)_0/T_c) (1 - T/T_c)^{\beta-1} \quad \dots(17)$$

From Eq. (17), the cross-over temperature (T_{co}) can be written as:

$$T_{co} = T_c [1 - \{ -3BT_c / (\beta(\Delta n)_0) \}^{1/(\beta-1)}] \quad \dots(18)$$

Further, for pure LCs, the molecular polarizabilities (α_e , α_o) can be easily determined if density and molecular weight of LC are known. In case of LC mixtures, it is quite difficult to find the molecular weight. Also Madhusudana²⁷ has shown that 1% error in the measurements of density leads to 11% error in the measurements of $(\alpha_e - \alpha_o)$. Therefore, the concept of normalized polarizability is used here, which eliminates the factor N containing both density and molecular weight. The normalized polarizability for extraordinary and ordinary rays are given by:

$$\alpha_e / \langle \alpha \rangle = (n_e^2 - 1) / (\langle n^2 \rangle - 1) \quad \dots(19)$$

$$\alpha_o / \langle \alpha \rangle = (n_o^2 - 1) / (\langle n^2 \rangle - 1) \quad \dots(20)$$

It is clear from Eqs 19 and 20 that normalized polarizability ($\alpha_e / \langle \alpha \rangle$, $\alpha_o / \langle \alpha \rangle$) are independent of density and molecular weight. Here $\langle \alpha \rangle$ is mean polarizability which is given as:

$$\langle \alpha \rangle = (\alpha_e + 2\alpha_o) / 3 \quad \dots(21)$$

The average molecular orientation is defined by an order parameter S

$$\langle S \rangle = \langle 3\cos^2\theta - 1 \rangle / 2 \quad \dots(22)$$

where θ is the angle between layer normal and long molecular axis.

The orientational order parameter can also be calculated using Vuks hypothesis²³.

Fig. 1 — Circles represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of refractive indices and average refractive index for ZLI 2141-000. Pentagons represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of refractive indices and average refractive index $(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$ for ZLI 2452

Table 3 — Calculation of the constants A , B , Δn_0 and β for both the samples

Samples	A	$B (\times 10^{-4})$	Δn_0	β
ZLI 2141-000	1.709	-5.533	0.237	0.2420
ZLI 2452	1.697	-4.989	0.220	0.2944

$$S(\Delta \alpha/\alpha) = (n_e^2 - n_o^2) / (\langle n^2 \rangle - 1) \quad \dots(23)$$

where $\Delta \alpha$ is the anisotropy of molecular polarizability.

For obtaining S , procedure of Haller²⁴ is followed. Factor $(\Delta \alpha/\alpha)$ is called scaling factor and is determined by plotting $\log [(n_e^2 - n_o^2) / (\langle n^2 \rangle - 1)]$ as a function of $\log (1 - T/T_c)$. The plot is a straight line and can be extrapolated to $T = 0$ K, intercept at $T = 0$ K gives the required scaling factor.

The temperature derivative of order parameter is also calculated and given by:

$$\frac{dS/dT}{(\Delta \alpha/\alpha)} = \frac{2[-SB(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2} + (n_e dn_e/dT - n_o dn_o/dT)]}{(\langle n^2 \rangle - 1)} \quad \dots(24)$$

In addition, a verification of the modified Vuks equation²⁰:

$$\langle n^2 \rangle + 2 \approx (10)^{1/2} \langle n \rangle - 0.5 \quad \dots(25)$$

and a semi-empirical relationship²¹

$$(\langle n^2 \rangle + 2) / (n_e + n_o) \approx 1.4 \quad \dots(26)$$

have also been made.

4 Results and Discussion

The clearing temperatures of LC samples ZLI 2141-000 and ZLI 2452 were obtained as 340.8 K and 382.2 K, respectively. As expected, the transition temperatures of both the samples were not sharp²⁸ as in case of pure nematic LC samples.

To make a fair comparison of various properties of two samples, all the graphs have been plotted with reduced temperature (T/T_c). The constants A , B , Δn_0 and β are calculated for both samples using Eqs (12) and (13) and their values are given in Table 3.

By substituting the values of above constants and clearing temperature in Eqs (14) and (15), we get expressions for n_e and n_o as a function of temperature (T).

In Fig. 1, discrete points from observations and continuous curves as a function of reduced temperature for n_e , n_o and $(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$ have been plotted. Observations for n_i are also shown on the same graph

in Fig. 1. As temperature increases, behaviour of n_e is different from n_o ; n_e depends strongly on temperature while the temperature dependence of n_o is weak. With the increase in temperature, n_e decreases throughout the entire nematic range while n_o decreases initially and then increases. Above the clearing point, the optical anisotropy vanishes and the isotropic refractive index (n_i) decreases with temperature as in normal organic liquids²⁹. It has been observed from Fig. 1 that the curves of n_e , n_o , $(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$, n_i for sample ZLI 2141-000 lie wholly above to that for ZLI 2452. The continuous line of $(\langle n^2 \rangle)^{1/2}$ is extrapolated into the isotropic region and it is found that the discrete points of n_i lie on the same line.

In Fig. 2, the birefringence (Δn) decreases gradually with increase in temperature and the two curves are found to be of similar nature. The value of β is greater for ZLI 2452 than that for ZLI 2141-000 which seems to be due to the presence of BCH in place of CB component in the latter.

Fig. 3 shows the temperature dependence of normalized polarizabilities for extraordinary ($\alpha_e/\langle \alpha \rangle$) and ordinary ($\alpha_o/\langle \alpha \rangle$) components. The behaviour of $\alpha_e/\langle \alpha \rangle$ is different from that of $\alpha_o/\langle \alpha \rangle$. $\alpha_e/\langle \alpha \rangle$

decreases while $\alpha_o/\langle \alpha \rangle$ increases with increase in temperature when T/T_c is 1, both approaches to unity. Further, the curve of $\alpha_e/\langle \alpha \rangle$ for ZLI 2141-000 lies above to that of ZLI 2452 while in the case of $\alpha_o/\langle \alpha \rangle$, the curve for ZLI 2141-000 lies below to that of ZLI 2452.

From Fig. 4, it is clear that the behaviour of order parameter (S) is similar to that of birefringence. Both reduce to zero as temperature approaches to T_c . The similarity in the behaviour of birefringence and order parameter is further investigated by plotting a graph between the two and the linear relationship is found between them as shown in Fig. 5.

Using Eqs (16) and (17), dn_e/dT and dn_o/dT as a function of reduced temperature are shown in Fig. 6. As in entire nematic range, n_e decreases continuously as the temperature increases, so dn_e/dT is always negative for both LC samples. However, dn_o/dT changes its sign from negative to positive at a particular temperature known as cross-over temperature (T_{co}). The value of cross-over temperature is different for two LC samples and found 324.14 K for ZLI 2141-000 and 364.74 K for ZLI 2452. Higher is the value of clearing temperature,

Fig. 2 — Circles represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of birefringence for ZLI 2141-000. Pentagons represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of birefringence for ZLI 2452

Fig. 3 — Circles represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of normalized polarizability for ZLI 2141-000. Pentagons represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of normalized polarizability for ZLI 2452

Fig. 4 — Circles represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of order parameter for ZLI 2141-000. Pentagons represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of order parameter for ZLI 2452

Fig. 5 — Circles represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of order parameter versus birefringence for ZLI 2141-000. Pentagons represent experimental data and solid line represent fitting curves of order parameter versus birefringence for ZLI 2452

Fig. 6 — Lines going upwards represent dn_o/dT and those going downwards represent dn_e/dT

greater is the value of cross-over temperature. All the calculations, linear fitting and plotting of graphs have been made using MATLABTM.

5 Conclusion

A slight modification to four parameter model¹⁹ is made and to verify it two LC samples ZLI 2141-000 and ZLI 2452 are used. The temperature variations of refractive indices are experimentally measured and various other properties are calculated using experimental data and the modified model. The discrete experimental points and continuous curves are plotted on the same graph. A very close agreement between the two for various properties of LC samples is obtained.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the assistance provided by Dr Anil Kr Jain, Principal, Vardhaman College, Bijnor and Sri Satya Prakash and Dr Ashok Kr Jain, Physics Department, for encouragement.

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